

Deliverable report for

Sustainable Energy Harvesting Systems Based on Innovative Mine Waste Recycling

Project 101058632

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All WPs and Tasks

1 TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	Table of contents.....	3
2	Abbreviations and Acronyms.....	4
3	Executive summary.....	5
4	Introduction: WP6.....	6
4.1	Objectives of WP6.....	6
4.2	WP6 activity.....	6
4.2.1	Deliverables and Milestones.....	7
5	Task 6.3: Training activities.....	10
5.1	Approach.....	10
5.2	Strategic Training Guidelines	10
5.3	Activities	11
5.3.1	EPMA Summer Schools.....	11
5.3.2	ASGMI events	17
5.3.2.1	General objectives.....	17
5.3.2.2	Specific objectives.....	18
5.3.2.3	Target audience	18
5.3.2.4	Training format	18
5.3.2.5	Content of the course	18
5.3.2.6	Evaluation of training.....	19
5.3.3	LNEG at the “Materials for Energy Transition” Summer School	20
5.3.4	Other training opportunities	23
5.3.4.1	Training in synergy with clustered projects and initiatives	23
5.3.4.2	The START webinars	23
5.3.5	Final Workshop	23

2 ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

Acronym	Description
D&C	Dissemination and Communication
ExCom	START's Executive Committee (WP leaders)
WP	Work Package
PM	Powder Metallurgy
MEL	Mining Environmental Liabilities

3 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The present deliverable reports on the activity of Task 6.3 “Training activities” in the period 1st June 2023 – 31st May 2024¹ (M13 to M24 of the START project).

A document that is labelled “Strategic Training Guidelines” was completed and approved. It outlines the protocol for the development of the training plan within the START project, with a dual objective: to ensure maximum visibility of the START project and the work that is being carried out, and to ensure the transfer of high-value knowledge present within partners and generated by the project and to promote learning opportunities and building capacities with and for young scientists. The guidelines will ensure the highest quality of the training (and mentoring) actions so that the attendees and the project can benefit optimally.

On the practical side, some training events have already been carried out:

- A 30' START lecture during the EPMA 2023 Powder Metallurgy Summer School (Dresden, 17-21 July 2023) with an audience of 60 students.
- A presentation of the START project on 6-8 September 2023 during the 2nd edition of the summer school “Materials for Energy Transition”, organised by the technical division “Materials for Energy” of the Portuguese Society of Materials in Porto, Portugal, with an audience of 20 students.

More training events are being organised and imagined, especially:

- EPMA is organising another activity in the 2024 Summer School in Alessandria (Italy), 15-19 July 2024, consisting in demonstrations of thermoelectric devices.
- ASGMI is organizing a bachelor's/master's student training workshop over many days in September 2024.
- In the framework of the clustering activities (Task 6.4) START is trying to plan joint training activities that can be organised together with other projects or initiatives that share some of the main interests of the project, like mine waste exploitation, raw materials issues, energy harvesting, green energy, etc.
- Other events not purely imagined as trainings (like the START webinars) will help educating on the topics of the project.
- The Final Training Workshop, focused on sustainability, close to the end of the project, whose organisation will not start before 2025.

¹ For practical reasons linked to text reviewing and submission, some details related to the month of May could not be reported and will be dealt with in the next deliverable of the same series, D6.11 (M36).

4 INTRODUCTION: WP6

4.1 OBJECTIVES OF WP6

The overall objective of WP6 is to disseminate widely the results of the START project to maximise its impact. The key objectives of this work package are:

- To raise awareness of all relevant parties (scientific and industrial communities, general public and policy makers) about START project activities in a coherent and consistent manner.
- To ensure an effective dissemination of the technical and scientific results of START project to the scientific and industrial communities.
- To ensure an effective communication of the achievements of START project to the wider scientific and technical communities, policy makers and the general public.
- To elaborate the Dissemination and Communication Plan (DCP) and update it when required.

Various communication activities are envisaged to disseminate the on-going and final project findings:

- Participations in congresses, workshops, webinars
- Training events
- Websites
- Scientific papers
- Newsletters and other publications
- Participation in trade fairs and exhibitions
- Other activities, etc.

EPMA, leading the WP, ensures a broad dissemination of the project progress and outcomes in Europe through its well-established network and website and its annual events and frequent Sectoral and Working Group meetings, even after the completion of the project. Nevertheless, all partners are required to collaborate in dissemination and communication by delivering content and executing some dissemination subtasks.

4.2 WP6 ACTIVITY

The activity of WP6 is organised in 5 Tasks, whose scope and activities will be explained in the main chapters of this report.

- Task 6.1: Specific project dissemination and communication tools
- Task 6.2: Technical and scientific dissemination
- Task 6.3: Training activities
- Task 6.4: Clustering
- Task 6.5: Final event

The GANTT chart for WP6 (Figure 1) shows the start and end of each task. As can be seen, Tasks 6.1, 6.2 and 6.4 have already begun in the first months of the project, whereas Task 6.3 started just at M12 (and Task 6.5 will only start in Year 4, rather close to the end of the project).

4.2.1 Deliverables and Milestones

The WP contains many deliverables, 15 out of a total of 39 for the whole project, but on the other hand only one milestone, that has already been achieved in M03 (August 2022).

The deliverables, also visible in Figure 2 can be grouped in the following categories:

- D6.1 - Creation of the project website, graphical identity and other online tools (M02): This deliverable describes the project's website, addresses the inherent need of the project to develop the START graphical identity, together with all the other online tools designed to support objectives of WP6 (*Submitted and approved*).
- D6.2 - Dissemination and Communication Plan (M03): Document outlining the most efficient strategy and means for implementing the dissemination and communication activities (*Submitted and approved*).
- D6.3, D6.4, D6.6, D6.7, D6.9, D6.10, D6.12, D6.13 - Dissemination, outreach and clustering activities (M06, M12, M18, M24, M30, M36, M42, M48): Report to be prepared on a 6-month basis, describing all the dissemination, communication, outreach and clustering activities with other EU projects and initiatives that have been developed and implemented and plans on how to proceed (*D6.3 and D6.4 have been submitted and approved, D6.6 was submitted, D6.7 is being presented at the end of M24, D6.9 upcoming in 6 months*).
- D6.5, D6.8, D6.11, D6.14 - Training activities (M12, M24, M36, M48): Report on a 12-month basis describing the training activities implemented (*D6.5 was submitted and approved, D6.8 is the present report, D6.11 upcoming in 12 months*).
- D6.15 - Final Event (M46): Final event conference report.

Concerning milestones, only one was envisaged, namely Milestone 08:

- MS08: Project Website (M03) - Project website functional and accessible

The website was in fact the key stone of all further dissemination, so it needed to be started as early as possible and was set as a milestone. It has been achieved as planned (declared on 22 August 2022 on the Funding & Tenders Portal, the website being also subject of Deliverable D6.1).

Figure 1: GANTT chart for WP6. M01 = June 2022; M48 = May 2026. Bordered in orange, the period covered by this deliverable D6.8 (M13-M24).

Deliverables												
Work Package No	Deliverable Related No	Deliverable No	Deliverable Name	Description	Lead Beneficiary	Type	Dissemination Level	Due Date	New Due Date (if delay)	Delivery Date	Approval Date	Status
WP6	D6.1	D19	Creation of the project website, graphical identity and other online tools	This deliverable describes the project's website, addresses the inherent need of the project to develop the START graphical identity, together with all the other online tools designed to support objectives of WP6.	EPMA	DEC	PU	31 Jul 2022		29 Jul 2022	31 Aug 2022	Approved
WP6	D6.2	D20	Dissemination and Communication Plan	Document outlining the most efficient strategy and means for implementing the dissemination and communication activities.	EPMA	R	PU	31 Aug 2022		30 Aug 2022	06 Dec 2023	Approved
WP6	D6.3	D21	Dissemination, outreach and clustering activities - M6	Report to be prepared on a 6-month basis, describing all the dissemination, communication, outreach and clustering activities with other EU projects and initiatives that have been developed and implemented and plans on how to proceed.	EPMA	R	PU	30 Nov 2022		30 Nov 2022	06 Dec 2023	Approved
WP6	D6.4	D22	Dissemination, outreach and clustering activities - M12	Report to be prepared on a 6-month basis, describing all the dissemination, communication, outreach and clustering activities with other EU projects and initiatives that have been developed and implemented and plans on how to proceed.	EPMA	R	PU	31 May 2023		31 May 2023	06 Dec 2023	Approved
WP6	D6.5	D23	Training activities - M12	Report to be prepared on a 12-month basis describing the training activities implemented.	ASGMI	R	PU	31 May 2023		31 May 2023	06 Dec 2023	Approved
WP6	D6.6	D24	Dissemination, outreach and clustering activities - M18	Report to be prepared on a 6-month basis, describing all the dissemination, communication, outreach and clustering activities with other EU projects and initiatives that have been developed and implemented and plans on how to proceed.	EPMA	R	PU	30 Nov 2023		30 Nov 2023		Submitted
WP6	D6.7	D25	Dissemination, outreach and clustering activities - M24	Report to be prepared on a 6-month basis, describing all the dissemination, communication, outreach and clustering activities with other EU projects and initiatives that have been developed and implemented and plans on how to proceed.	EPMA	R	PU	31 May 2024				Pending
WP6	D6.8	D26	Training activities - M24	Report to be prepared on a 12-month basis describing the training activities implemented.	ASGMI	R	PU	31 May 2024				Pending
WP6	D6.9	D27	Dissemination, outreach and clustering activities - M30	Report to be prepared on a 6-month basis, describing all the dissemination, communication, outreach and clustering activities with other EU projects and initiatives that have been developed and implemented and plans on how to proceed.	EPMA	R	PU	30 Nov 2024				Pending
WP6	D6.10	D28	Dissemination, outreach and clustering activities - M36	Report to be prepared on a 6-month basis, describing all the dissemination, communication, outreach and clustering activities with other EU projects and initiatives that have been developed and implemented and plans on how to proceed.	EPMA	R	PU	31 May 2025				Pending
WP6	D6.11	D29	Training activities - M36	Report to be prepared on a 12-month basis describing the training activities implemented.	ASGMI	R	PU	31 May 2025				Pending
WP6	D6.12	D30	Dissemination, outreach and clustering activities - M42	Report to be prepared on a 6-month basis, describing all the dissemination, communication, outreach and clustering activities with other EU projects and initiatives that have been developed and implemented and plans on how to proceed.	EPMA	R	PU	30 Nov 2025				Pending
WP6	D6.13	D31	Dissemination, outreach and clustering activities - M48	Report to be prepared on a 6-month basis, describing all the dissemination, communication, outreach and clustering activities with other EU projects and initiatives that have been developed and implemented and plans on how to proceed.	EPMA	R	PU	31 May 2026				Pending
WP6	D6.14	D32	Training activities - M48	Report to be prepared on a 12-month basis describing the training activities implemented.	ASGMI	R	PU	31 May 2026				Pending
WP6	D6.15	D33	Final Event	Final event conference report.	ASGMI	R	PU	31 Mar 2026				Pending

	To be completed on the current year
	Deadline approaching
	Submitted
	Approved

Figure 2: List of WP6 deliverables, with deadlines and status.

5 TASK 6.3: TRAINING ACTIVITIES

Task leader: EPMA; Participants: All; M12 to M48

5.1 APPROACH

This task aims to ensure the transfer of high-value knowledge present within partners and generated by the project to promote learning opportunities and building capacities with and for young scientists. We will make use of established and new training activities, to funnel knowledge to students, young engineers, and experts:

- A strategic document on how to present, promote, call, recruit and orient and mentor young students and researchers into the project.
- Project lectures during the EPMA PM Summer School². During the 4 years of the project, we plan to reach at least 200 students by this activity (normally 50-60 participants in each edition). This includes the preparation of a lecture, updated every year, about START activities.
- ASGMI has significant experience working with Mining Environmental Liabilities. In the past, several workshops and events have been organized on this topic³. ASGMI is developing learning material based on the already existing products & experience and will add new information and results from START (mainly from WP 2). The objective is to hold a free online training course open to bachelor's and master's degree young students where they can interact with the researchers, ask questions and learn details of the project.
- During a final Training Workshop for scientists and industry members, focused on sustainability of the developed know-how. Lecturers from the consortium will give presentation to external participants.

5.2 STRATEGIC TRAINING GUIDELINES

A document named "Strategic Training Guidelines" was drafted collaboratively using the START project SharePoint at the beginning of the task and was reviewed and finalised recently. This is an important first step to take a uniform approach to the topic, avoid errors and maximise the impact of the training activities.

This internal document contains the following chapters:

- Plan for training within START. Main training events and tools, expected participation and targets, scope of the trainings, evaluation of training, reporting of training.
- Guidelines for training: how to plan, promote, present.
- Guidelines for mentoring: how to call, recruit and mentor.

The document is available on the project SharePoint.

² <https://summerschool.epma.com/>

³ <https://asgmi.org/grupo-de-expertos-en-pasivosambientales-mineros-2/>

5.3 ACTIVITIES

The activity in training runs along some different lines, relying on the expertise of some key training partners, with experience in organising training events, for students of different levels and for experienced and educated trainees.

5.3.1 EPMA Summer Schools

The EPMA Powder Metallurgy Summer School⁴ is organised by the European Powder Metallurgy Association (EPMA) with support from its members. In fact, founded in 1989, EPMA is the leading powder metallurgy (PM) trade association representing the interests of the entire European PM community, and promoting PM technology throughout the world. The Summer School, that started in 1998 and reaches this year its 22nd edition, was already described in detail in D6.5⁵, so we encourage checking that for more information.

In 2022 only a quick update on START – one slide with the general features of the project, its approach, expected results and impact, its relevance for the Green Deal - was given by B. Vicenzi (EPMA) during his initial address to the attendees (60 plus the speakers and the local organizers) in the 2022 edition of the Summer School, that was held from 20 to 24 June in Universidad de Castilla-La Mancha in Ciudad Real (Spain).

The 2023 edition was held in Dresden and was the 21st in the series. This was also the third time the school was hosted in Dresden, after the first edition in 1998 (in Meissen, just a few kilometres away from Dresden) and that of 2011. The premises of the Fraunhofer institute IFAM (Institut für Angewandte Materialien, Institute for Applied Materials) hosted on 17-21 July 60 trainees chosen among the 102 potential trainees that had applied within the deadline of 3rd May 2023. The school was thus largely overbooked, as a demonstration of the success of the format.

The programme was arranged by EPMA, together with some academic EPMA members that take care of the technical content of the school and is available in Figure 3. START was presented again by B. Vicenzi (EPMA) during his opening speech on Monday 17th July (Figure 4), as in 2022.

Among the several lectures, as always, there were topics relevant for START (“Powder Manufacturing and Characterization”, “Alternative Methods and Innovative Sintering”), but in particular on Friday 21st, 13:00 – 13:30, A. Bianchin (MBN) closed the series of lectures by giving a presentation titled “Thermoelectric Materials and the START Project” (Figure 5 and Figure 6).

⁴ <https://summerschool.epma.com/>

⁵ <https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/documents/downloadPublic?documentIds=080166e5fc732351&appId=PPGMS>

EPMA
European Powder Metallurgy Association

Powder Metallurgy Summer School

17 July - 21 July 2023 - Dresden, Germany

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Programme

Please note this programme may be subject to change.

Monday 17 July		
Time	Topic	Speaker
08:30 - 09:00	Presentation of EPMA & IFAM	Dr Bruno Vicenzi (EPMA) & Prof Thomas Weißgärber (Fraunhofer IFAM Dresden)
09:00 - 10:00	Introduction to Materials Science	Prof Alberto Molinari (University of Trento)
10:00 - 11:00	Introduction to PM	Prof Marco Actis Grande (Politecnico di Torino)
11:00 - 11:30	Coffee Break	
11:30 - 12:30	Powder Manufacturing and Characterization	Dr Dimitris Chasoglou (Hoganas AB)
12:30 - 13:30	Shaping Technologies	Dr Jose Manuel Sanchez Moreno (CEIT)
13:30 - 14:30	Lunch	
14:30 - 15:30	Fundamentals of Sintering	Prof Thomas Weißgärber (Fraunhofer IFAM Dresden; TU Dresden)
15:30 - 16:30	Liquid Phase Sintering	Dr Johannes Trapp (Fraunhofer IFAM Dresden)
16:30 - 17:30	Coffee Break in Poster Area	
19:30 - 21:30	Welcome Reception	

Tuesday 18 July		
Time	Topic	Speaker
08:30 - 09:30	Sintering Atmospheres	Prof Christian Gierl-Mayer (TU Wien)
09:30 - 10:30	Post Sintering Treatments	Prof Monika Campos (Universidad Carlos III de Madrid)
10:30 - 11:00	Coffee Break	
11:00 - 12:00	Properties of PM Parts	Prof Alberto Molinari (University of Trento)
12:00 - 13:00	Furnace Technology	Mr Michael Kanaan (CREMER Thermoprozessanlagen)
13:00 - 14:00	Lunch	
14:00 - 15:00	Calphad Method in PM	Prof Raquel Oro de Calderon (TU Wien)
15:00 - 16:00	Modeling	Prof Dr Christoph Broeckmann (RWTH Aachen University)
16:00 - 16:30	Coffee Break	
16:30 - 17:30	Hot Isostatic Pressing	Mr Anders Magnusson (Quintus Technologies)
17:30 - 19:00	Lab Tour	
19:00 - 22:00	Social Evening	

Wednesday 19 July		
Time	Topic	Speaker
08:30 - 09:30	Metal Injection Molding (I)	Prof Gemma Herranz (UCLM Spain)
09:30 - 10:30	Metal Injection Molding (II): Case studies, innovations and new frontiers	Prof Frank Petzoldt (Fraunhofer IFAM)
10:30 - 11:00	Coffee Break	
11:00 - 12:00	Additive Manufacturing (I) LPBF and SEBM	Mrs Marie Franke-Jurisch (Fraunhofer IFAM Dresden)
12:00 - 13:00	Additive Manufacturing (II) Sinterbased AM Technologies	Dr Thomas Studnicky (Fraunhofer IFAM Dresden)
13:00 - 14:00	Lunch	
14:00 - 15:00	Sustainability in PM	Mr Babak Kianian (Hoganas AB)
15:00 - 16:30	Group A - Case Study	Prof Christian Gierl-Mayer & Prof Marco Actis Grande
15:00 - 16:30	Group B - Lab Work	
16:30 - 17:00	Coffee Break	
17:00 - 18:30	Group A - Case Study	Prof Christian Gierl-Mayer & Prof Marco Actis Grande
17:00 - 18:30	Group B - Lab Work	
19:00 - 22:00	Dinner	

Thursday 20 July		
Time	Topic	Speaker
08:30 - 09:30	Low Alloy Steels	Prof Herbert Dänninger (TU Wien)
09:30 - 10:30	Special Steels	Dr Inigo Iturriza (CEIT)
10:30 - 11:00	Coffee Break	
11:00 - 12:00	Light Metals	Prof Thomas Weißgärber (Fraunhofer IFAM Dresden; TU Dresden)
12:00 - 13:00	High Temperature Materials	Prof José Manuel Torralba (IMDEA)
13:00 - 14:00	Lunch	
14:00 - 15:00	Alternative Methods and Innovative Sintering	Prof Lars Nyborg (Chalmers)
15:00 - 16:30	Group B - Case Study	Prof Christian Gierl-Mayer & Prof Marco Actis Grande
15:00 - 16:30	Group A - Lab Work	
16:30 - 17:00	Coffee Break	
17:00 - 18:30	Group B - Case Study	Prof Christian Gierl-Mayer & Prof Marco Actis Grande
17:00 - 18:30	Group A - Lab Work	

Friday 21 July		
Time	Topic	Speaker
08:30 - 09:30	PM Materials for Hydrogen Production	Dr Christian Bernackner (Fraunhofer IFAM Dresden)
09:30 - 10:30	PM Materials for Hydrogen Storage	Dr Felix Heubner (Fraunhofer IFAM Dresden)
10:30 - 11:00	Coffee Break	
11:00 - 12:00	Hard Materials	Dr Steven Moseley (Hill AG)
12:00 - 13:00	Soft Magnetic Materials	Dr Mark Dougan (AMES SA)
13:00 - 13:30	Thermoelectric Materials and the START Project	Mr Hao Yin (TEGnology) & Mr Avise Bianchin (MBN Nanomaterialia)
13:30 - 14:00	Certificates distribution	
14:00 - 15:00	Lunch	

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Figure 3: Programme of the EPMA Summer School 2023 in Dresden, Germany.

Figure 4: Highlights of the START project presented by B. Vicenzi of EPMA during the opening presentation at the 21st EPMA PM Summer School in Dresden, Germany

Figure 5: A. Bianchin (MBN) presenting “Thermoelectric Materials and the START Project” at the 21st EPMA PM Summer School in Dresden, Germany.

Figure 6: A. Bianchin (MBN) presenting “Thermoelectric Materials and the START Project” at the 21st EPMA PM Summer School in Dresden, Germany.

After the school, a feedback questionnaire is always circulated, where detailed evaluation of all lectures is asked, under several aspects (but no evaluation of students’ actual learning during the school is carried out). Among the questions, one is “How would you rate the coverage of each of the following areas?”. The presentation on thermoelectrics scored, on a scale from 4 to 10, a value of 7.83 (compared to an average of 8.70 for all topics), which could be improved but is still a very positive evaluation.

In 2024 the Summer School will be in Italy, (Alessandria, from 15th to 19th July) hosted by the Politecnico di Torino – Alessandria Campus. The format will be slightly different (Figure 7), as there will be a little more time for the lab experiences, while the usual time for presentations will be reduced from 1h to 45min.

The applications have again exceeded the available places (83 against a maximum of 65 trainees), and the selection is ongoing.

As we had already planned, we will not hold another lecture on START (apart from the small introduction by B. Vicenzi in the introductory speech), but rather offer an experience about thermoelectric materials. The structure of that experience will include a few introductory words to explain what waste heat is, what are thermoelectric materials and how they can be produced (with a focus on PM routes, as this is the target of the school), and then a small demo experience with the use of a thermoelectric device on a heated surface, to show how electricity can be harvested using waste heat. This will be given by H. Yin (TEGnology), using a device that the company already developed as a demo for exhibitions (Figure 8, Figure 9 and Figure 10). It is planned to have two demonstrations for two separate groups of trainees, one on Wednesday morning and one on Thursday morning, during the respective lab and case study activities.

After the school, we will again collect information on the interest aroused by the activity among the trainees.

Powder Metallurgy Summer School
15 July - 19 July 2024 - Alessandria, Italy

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Programme 2024

Please note this programme may be subject to change.

Monday 15 July 2024		
Time	Topic	Speaker
08:30 - 09:00	Introduction & Presentation of EPMA	Dr Bruno Vicenzi (EPMA) & Prof Marco Actis Grande (Politecnico di Torino)
09:00 - 09:45	Introduction to Materials Science	Prof Alberto Molinari (University of Trento)
09:45 - 10:30	Introduction to PM	Prof Marco Actis Grande (Politecnico di Torino)
10:30 - 11:00	Coffee Break	
11:00 - 11:45	Powder Manufacturing and Characterization	Dr Dimitris Chasoglou (Höganäs AB)
11:45 - 12:30	Shaping Technologies - Die Compaction	Dr Jose Manuel Sanchez Moreno (CEIT)
12:30 - 14:00	Lunch	
14:00 - 14:45	Fundamentals of Sintering	Dr Johannes Trapp (Fraunhofer IFAM Dresden)
14:45 - 15:30	Liquid Phase Sintering	Mrs Cinzia Menapace (University of Trento)
15:30 - 16:15	Sintering Atmospheres	Prof Christian Gierl-Mayer (TU Wien)
16:15 - 16:45	Coffee Break	
16:45 - 17:30	Post Sintering Treatments	Prof José Manuel Torralba (IMDEA)
17:30 - 18:15	Poster & Students presentations	
20:30 - 23:00	Welcome Reception	

Tuesday 16 July 2024		
Time	Topic	Speaker
08:30 - 09:45	Atomizing Group A1	
09:45 - 10:30	Properties of PM parts	Prof Alberto Molinari (University of Trento)
10:30 - 11:00	Coffee Break	
11:00 - 11:45	Furnace Technology	Mr Michael Kanaan (CREMER Thermoprozessanlagen)
11:45 - 12:30	Hot Isostatic Pressing	Mr Anders Magnusson (Quintus Technologies)
12:30 - 14:00	Lunch	
14:00 - 14:45	Calphad Method in PM	Prof Raquel Oro de Calderon (TU Wien)
14:45 - 15:30	Modelling	Prof Dr Christoph Broeckmann (RWTH Aachen University)
15:30 - 16:15	Light Metals	Prof Thomas Weißgärber (Fraunhofer IFAM Dresden; TU Dresden)
16:15 - 16:45	Coffee Break	
16:45 - 17:30	Sustainability in PM	Mrs Sofia Poulkidou (Höganäs AB)
17:30 - 18:15	Soft Magnetic Materials	Dr Mark Dougan (AMES SA)

Wednesday 17 July 2024		
Time	Topic	Speaker
08:30 - 09:45	Atomizing Group A2	
09:00 - 10:30	Case Study Group 2	Prof Christian Gierl-Mayer (TU Wien)
09:45 - 12:30	Lab Work Group 1	
10:30 - 11:00	Coffee Break	
11:00 - 12:30	Case Study Group 2	Prof Christian Gierl-Mayer (TU Wien)
12:30 - 14:00	Lunch	
14:00 - 14:45	Hard Materials I	Dr Steven Moseley (Hilti AG)
14:45 - 15:30	Hard Materials II	Prof Susanne Norgren (Sandvik)
15:30 - 16:15	Special Steels	Dr Inigo Irujoza (CEIT)
16:15 - 16:45	Coffee Break	
16:45 - 17:30	Low Alloy Steels	Prof Herbert Damminger (TU Wien)
17:30 - 18:15	Additive Manufacturing (I) Alloys Development	Prof Riccardo Casati (Politecnico di Milano)
20:30 - 23:00	Summer School Dinner	

Thursday 18 July 2024		
Time	Topic	Speaker
08:30 - 09:45	Atomizing Group A3	
09:00 - 10:30	Case Study Group 1	Prof Christian Gierl-Mayer (TU Wien)
09:45 - 12:30	Lab Work Group 2	
10:30 - 11:00	Coffee Break	
11:00 - 12:30	Case Study Group 1	Prof Christian Gierl-Mayer (TU Wien)
12:30 - 14:00	Lunch	
14:00 - 14:45	Metal Injection Molding I	Prof Gemma Herranz (Universidad de Castilla La Mancha)
14:45 - 15:30	Metal Injection Molding II	Prof Frank Petzoldt (Petzoldt Consulting)
15:30 - 16:15	Additive Manufacturing (II) PBF/DDED	Prof Diego Manfredi (Politecnico di Torino)
16:15 - 16:45	Coffee Break	
16:45 - 17:30	Additive Manufacturing (III) BJ/3D Printing	Dr Cristina Berges (Universidad de Castilla La Mancha)
17:30 - 18:15	RESQTOOL Project	Dr Gian Pietro De Gaudenzi (FILMS SpA)

Friday 19 July 2024		
Time	Topic	Speaker
08:30 - 09:45	Summary of Lab Activities	
09:45 - 10:30	High Temperature Materials	Prof Monica Campos (Universidad Carlos III de Madrid)
10:30 - 11:00	Coffee Break	
11:00 - 11:45	Alternative Methods & Innovative Sintering	Prof Lars Nyborg (Chalmers)
11:45 - 12:30	PM Materials for Hydrogen Technology	Mr Christian Bernäcker (Fraunhofer IFAM Dresden)
12:30 - 14:00	Lunch	

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Figure 7: Provisional programme of the EPMA Summer School 2024 in Alessandria, Italy.

Figure 8: Example of thermoelectric device setup similar to what will be demonstrated at the EPMA Summer School 2024: TEGnology's autonomous power supply unit, SensEver-HSI.

Figure 9: Example of thermoelectric device setup similar to what will be demonstrated at the EPMA Summer School 2024.

Figure 10: Example of thermoelectric device setup similar to what will be demonstrated at the EPMA Summer School 2024, here for remote sensing and smart data collection.

5.3.2 ASGMI events

In the previous deliverable D 6.5, we already gave evidence and examples of how ASGMI has extensive experience in organizing workshops, both virtual and face-to-face, on various topics related to mineral resources and mining environmental liabilities which are among the subject of work for the expert groups that are part of the Association.

Under this experience, ASGMI is organizing a virtual training workshop within the START project. The workshop is aimed at university or graduate students. The speakers for the workshop are members of ASGMI's Expert Groups on Environmental Liabilities and Mineral Resources, from various countries in Latin America, Spain, and Portugal, as well as members of the Academy and international collaborators from other European projects. The workshop, titled **"Mining Environmental Liabilities and Secondary Raw Materials,"** will be held online between **September 25 and October 3, 2024**, and will total 10 hours of training.

Below we present the objectives and preliminary program of the workshop, developed according to the Training Guidelines Document.

5.3.2.1 General objectives

The responsible management of mining environmental liabilities and the reuse of secondary raw materials emerge, at present, as fundamental pillars for the sustainable development of the extractive industry.

This course arises in response to the growing need to train professionals capable of addressing the environmental challenges inherent in mining activities and, simultaneously, efficiently harnessing available resources. The primary objective of this training is to provide participants with an in-depth understanding of mining processes, their environmental and social impacts, and to equip them with the necessary tools for the identification, assessment, and remediation of environmental liabilities.

Furthermore, the course will focus on exploring the possibilities offered by the circular economy and the reuse of secondary raw materials as strategic avenues to reduce the environmental footprint of mining and promote more sustainable practices. This course is designed for professionals, from engineers and geologists to environmental management professionals and entrepreneurs interested in implementing more responsible and efficient practices in the mining sector.

A second objective of this training is to provide a greater visibility to the START project and the work that is being carried out within a community of students.

5.3.2.2 Specific objectives

The specific objectives within the Virtual training related to mining environmental liabilities and secondary raw materials are:

- To improve the students' knowledge within the field of raw materials sustainability and renewable energies and their role in today's world.
- To spread awareness within the students about passive liabilities, their identification and origins and their impact on the environment, goods and living beings.
- To improve their knowledge on remediation of mining passive liabilities, their protocols of remediation and tailing processing.
- To develop a greater understanding of topics related to the passive liabilities and the objectives of the START project, such as sustainability, ecological impact, circularity and mining waste.

5.3.2.3 Target audience

The target audience for the training proposed are postgraduate students from fields such as geology, mining engineering, or environmental engineering.

The number of registrations, given ASGMI's experience in organizing virtual workshops, could exceed 100 participants. However, to facilitate dialogue between students and instructors, it will be limited to 30 students.

5.3.2.4 Training format

The training will be conducted virtually in several sessions, each lasting no more than 2 hours.

The number of total hours will be 10 (5 sessions of 2 hours).

The language of the training will be English.

5.3.2.5 Content of the course

The contents of the course will be the following:

Module 1: Fundamentals of Mining Environmental Liabilities:

- Fundamentals:
- Types of environmental liabilities in mining.
- Methodology for conducting an inventory of dormant or abandoned mines.
- Sampling Protocol:
- Sample collection, identification and classification of samples.
- Field and laboratory tests.

Module 2: Identification of environmental impacts for goods and people.

- Environmental impacts.
- Geodynamics or other processes present in the environment.
- Safety issues for people and prevention of occupational hazards associated with mining environmental liabilities (MELs).

Module 3: Remediation of Environmental Liabilities:

- Techniques and technologies for remediation of MELs depending on their classification and environment.
- Restoration of affected ecosystems.
- Cases of remediation in the field and results.

Module 4: Reuse of Secondary Raw Materials:

- Basics of the circular economy.
- Recycling of industrial wastes into sustainable building materials.
- Technological innovations for resource recovery. The START Project case.
- Procedure for filling out the inventory form for abandoned or paralyzed mines.

Module 5: Environmental Management and Corporate Social Responsibility:

- Strategies for sustainable management.
- Integration of social responsibility in mining management.
- International certifications and standards.

The details of the contents of each module are still being developed by the experts, so they may be subject to slight variations.

As mentioned above, the mentors teaching each class are members of ASGMI's expert groups on environmental liabilities and mineral resources, some of whom are involved in the START project, members of the Academy, and international collaborators participating in other European projects.

5.3.2.6 Evaluation of training

Once the course is over, an evaluation of the lectures will be requested from the attendees with a questionnaire, so that START will be provided with feedback regarding the presentations.

The students' learning during the course as such will be evaluated with a short questionnaire with general questions about the lessons given in the course. At the end of the course, approved students will be given a certificate of attendance.

To promote the virtual course, ASGMI has started by disseminating information about the workshop on its [website](#)⁶ (Figure 11), and social media advertisement will follow soon, once the programme will be better defined (some lecturers are still in the process of confirming their participation). Additionally, in the months leading up to the workshop, ASGMI will develop internal communication actions through its Expert Groups and member Geological Services.

Figure 11: First graphics for the advertisement for the Virtual Training Workshop organised by ASGMI.

On the other hand, ASGMI's relationships with other international organizations such as EuroGeo Surveys, the European Federation of Geologists, EIT Raw Materials, and professional associations from various countries will ensure its widespread dissemination.

Further communication about it will be made through the START website and its social media channels.

5.3.3 LNEG at the “Materials for Energy Transition” Summer School

The 2nd edition of the “Materials for Energy Transition” Summer School (Figure 12), a three-day event organized by Sociedade Portuguesa de Materiais (SPM), Ordem dos Engenheiros Região Norte, INL and LNEG, took place in Porto on 6-8th September 2023.

Within the session dedicated to “Advanced Energy Materials”, José Brito Correia (LNEG) delivered a lecture titled “Projeto START – Utilização de tetraedrites como material termoelétrico” (“START Project – Use of tetrahedrites as thermoelectric material”) to an audience of 20 Portuguese PhD and Master’s students (Figure 13). This presentation covered the project’s focus on mechanochemical synthesis, spark plasma sintering, and the application of tetrahedrites in thermoelectric materials. It served as an excellent platform to disseminate the project’s activities among the student community.

⁶ <https://asgmi.org/en/curso-virtual-pasivos-ambientales-mineros-y-materias-primas-secundarias/>

Furthermore, Filipe Neves (LNEG) participated in a round table discussion at the conclusion of the session (Figure 14). This provided an opportunity to highlight the project's objectives within the context of current energy transition challenges and emphasize the crucial role of materials in this endeavour.

Figure 12: Banner of the 2nd Edition of the “Materials for Energy Transition” Summer School, Porto (PT), 6-8th September 2023.

Figure 13: Presentation by José Brito Correia (LNEG) at the 2nd edition of the Summer School “Materials for Energy Transition” in Porto, 7th September 2023.

Figure 14 Round table including Filipe Neves (LNEG) at the 2nd edition of the Summer School “Materials for Energy Transition” in Porto, 7th September 2023.

The same organizers are preparing in July 2024 (22nd-24th) the third edition of the summer school⁷ at the premises of the Aveiro University, Portugal (Figure 15). At the moment, the program is still being outlined but this year, differently from 2023 when we gave a lecture on the START project, only some distribution of material is foreseen, as well as the provision of promotional information about the project (roller banner and leaflets).

Figure 15: Banner of the 3rd Edition of the “Materials for Energy Transition” Summer School, Porto (PT), 22-24th July 2024.

⁷ <https://spmateriais.pt/site/3a-edicao-summer-school-materials-for-energy-transition/>

5.3.4 Other training opportunities

5.3.4.1 Training in synergy with clustered projects and initiatives

In the framework of the clustering activities (Task 6.4) START will see if joint training activities can be organised together with other projects or initiatives that share some of the main interests of the project, like mine waste exploitation, raw materials issues, energy harvesting, green energy, etc. No plan is present yet, but this would be a way to make the collaborations concrete and measurable.

5.3.4.2 The START webinars

Although not purely training events, also the webinars will disseminate useful information and educate to the topics of thermoelectricity, mine waste recovery, waste heat recovery, etc. Three of them had already been organised in the previous period, on 28/02/2023, 26/04/2023 and 31/05/2023 (details on these events can be retrieved in Deliverable D6.4. In Deliverable D6.7 the report about the organisation of 2 other webinars, on 14th March 2024 and 7th June 2024, is given.

5.3.5 Final Workshop

The final Training Workshop, according to what indicated in the initial proposal, will be both for scientists and industry members, and focused on sustainability of the developed know-how. Lecturers from the consortium will give presentation to external participants, probably in a hybrid format. The actual contents, the duration and all details will clearly be decided much later, beginning the organisation at the end of the third year of the project (May 2025).